

The Chemistry of Jute-lignin. Part. V. Chlorination of Lignin.

BY POLIN BEHARI SARKAR.

In a former paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 263) it has been shown by the author that jute-lignin is not essentially different from other lignins, as it gave similar products on potash fusion and that Cross and Bevan's formula cannot explain their formation. The original formula of Cross and Bevan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 12, 104) was arrived at by studying the chloro compound obtained directly from jute. The empirical formula ($C_{19}H_{18}O_9Cl_4$) was assigned to it. Chlorination of jute-fibre was according to these authors a process of simple substitution and they obtained mairougallol and leucogallol on sublimation of chlorolignin.

Since then chlorination of various woods and separated lignins has been studied by many investigators; the results obtained are, however, far from being concordant. Thus, Heuser and Sieber (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1913, 26, 801) by the chlorination of spruce-wood got a product with 22.7% of chlorine; Powell and Whittaker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 357) got from alkali-lignin a chloro compound whose Cl-content was 35.1% and Rassow and Zickmann (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1929, 123, 217) were able to isolate a chloro compound with 38.22% of chlorine. Strong (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1928, 47, 196r) repeated the experiment of Cross and Bevan and found that besides substitution, considerable oxidation took place when moist chlorine acted on jute-fibre, so that contrary to Cross and Bevan's results the amount of Cl evolved as HCl was twice that combined with lignin. Strong explained the reaction by equations on the basis of Cross and Bevan's formula. While Jonas (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1921, 34, 289) and Waenting (*ibid.*, 1928, 41, 977, 1001) obtained the same derivative under similar conditions; Rassow and Zickmann (*loc. cit.*) were unable to get a homogeneous chloro compound from pine-wood lignin. According to Freudenberg, Belz and Niemann (*Ber.*, 1929, 62, 1554) when lignin is brominated only substitution takes place, but no addition; on the other hand, Hibbert and Sankey (*Canadian J.*

Research, 1931, 4, 110) found that both addition and substitution took place. From chlorolignin obtained from sources other than jute, no worker could get any product by sublimation. The process of halogenation of lignin, therefore, requires a critical study and the present investigation was undertaken with a view to throw as much light as possible on the problem.

Contrary to the observations of Cross and Bevan (*Cellulose*, 1903, p. 137) it has been found that dry chlorine acts on jute fibre dried at 110° over P_2O_5 under vacuum and a yellow chloro compound was obtained. The presence of moisture facilitated the process to a great extent but even then all the lignin could not be obtained as chloride easily. If the jute was boiled with 1% KOH for one hour and then chlorinated, the reaction was complete in one hour. As the reaction proceeds in the absence of moisture, it cannot be said that the oxidising action of moist chlorine is necessary to disrupt the so-called chemical union between lignin and cellulose. The effect of alkali-boiling appears to be more physical than chemical, as almost all the alkali could be washed off after boiling, the absorption of 1-2% KOH is explained by the fact that part of the acetyl group in pectin is hydrolysed thereby, as will be shown later on. It cannot also be said that the free alkali reduces the acidity of the medium and facilitates chlorination as has been found by Hibbert and Sankey (*loc. cit.*). It is well known that considerable swelling takes place when cellulose matter is treated with alkali. It seems most probable that the boiling alkali merely increases the size of the pores and thereby makes the passage of chlorine into the fibre easier.

In the case of separated lignin, however, it has been found that moisture has absolutely no effect on chlorination. The chlorination of jute-fibre as well as of isolated lignin is attended with liberation of heat. As is to be expected with an exothermic reaction at low temperature more chlorine entered into lignin, the time being the same. When HCl-lignin was chlorinated at 60° for 4 hours the maximum chlorine-content was only 17.6%. This also was the case when chlorination was done with catalysts like iodine, $FeCl_3$ or $SbCl_3$. The influence of light has been found to be nil, it proceeded as rapidly in the dark as in direct sunlight. When lignin was chlorinated in aqueous suspension, a product was obtained which was to some extent soluble in water and had much lower methoxy value. It was also soluble in alcohol, acetone, phenol, acetic acid, etc. But if the medium was CCl_4 , the product was no longer soluble in water

and only sparingly soluble in the organic solvents; the percentage of methoxy was, however, considerably higher. This is obviously due to the oxidising action of chlorine in presence of moisture. In all cases of chlorination about 6 to 7% of methoxy was always lost even when lignin was chlorinated in CCl_4 suspension by dry chlorine. When vanillin was similarly chlorinated, chlorovanillin also suffered a loss of 3% of methoxy. Again, when methyl alcohol was the medium the percentage of chlorine in the product was nearly the same but the methoxy rose up; thus methylation also took place besides chlorination. Chloroform and glacial acetic acid behaved in the same way as CCl_4 . Working under identical conditions, a chloro compound with the same percentage of Cl was always obtained from lignin as well from jute.

By a comparative study of the chloro derivatives obtained directly from jute and separated lignin, it has been found that the two are identical in many respects: thus, both the reactions are exothermic and take place with evolution of HCl; both compounds have the same yellow colour, and they are both ash-free; both dissolve in dilute alkali with a deep brown colour and on precipitation with acids a compound is obtained which has the same low chlorine content, *viz.*, 17.71%. On heating up to 135-40° both of them evolve HCl and turn brown and the resulting compounds have the same chlorine content again, *viz.*, 17.80%. Both are free from furfural-yielding substances and on distillation with 12% HCl or 28% H_2SO_4 both yield formaldehyde. On sublimation, none gives any product. On re-chlorination in glacial acetic acid both give chloro compounds with the same higher chlorine content, *viz.*, 32.7%. Both of them reduce Fehling's solution readily and both give CO_2 when boiled with 12% HCl even in an atmosphere of hydrogen. When distilled with moderately strong NaOH a distillate is obtained from both, which gives iodoform with iodine and alkali.

The presence of double bond in lignin is still a matter of dispute. To explain the formation of rather stable ligno-sulphonic acids, Klason (*Ber.*, 1920, 53, 705, 1862, 1864) assumed an ethylene linkage in lignin. Hibbert and Sankey (*loc. cit.*) from the results of bromination concluded that lignin contained an unsaturated side-chain. In their recent formula for lignin, Kürschner and Schramek (*Tech. Chem. Papier-Zellstoff-Fabr.*, 1932, 29, 35) made provision for an ethylene linkage to show its analogy to coniferin

and account for the formation of acetic acid on hydrolysis and oxidation. Heuser (*Paper Trade J.*, 1930, 88, 75) also considers the presence of a double bond in lignin very probable. Mehta (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 961) even determined the iodine value of lignin as 139. But from the study of absorption spectra Herzog (*Zellstoff u. Papier.*, 1932, 12, 10) and Hillemer (*Ber.*, 1933, 66, 1600) conclude that the side-chain in lignin is saturated. Freudenberg and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) considered the bromination as substitution, but they did not present quantitative data. In the present investigation, this question has been decided by estimating the HCl evolved and Cl combined with lignin. In aqueous suspension lignin (separated) like jute itself, was oxidised by chlorine and the ratio, Cl combined to Cl as HCl was found to be considerably higher (about 1:3). In CCl_4 as medium it was found to be very approximately equal to 1. This was independent of time and temperature of chlorination. As the lignin isolated by HCl contains only traces of Cl (which cannot be estimated) it is clear that no HCl addition to any double bond has taken place during isolation. Nor can dry Cl act as an oxidising agent. These results, therefore, prove conclusively that side-chains in lignin are saturated.

In a previous paper it has been shown that the dioxymethylene group is characteristic of lignin and that much of it is lost during careless isolation (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 691). Chlorolignin from jute and lignin were purified by dissolving in alcohol and then in acetone and the final product still gave HCHO on distillation with acids. Thus, it cannot be due to any impurity associated with lignin. But the major portion of the $\text{O}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{O}$ group was lost during chlorination as was the case with the methoxy group as well. Cross and Bevan's formula as also all others except the one by Freudenberg (*Ber.*, 1929, 62, 1814) does not contain this group. The former cannot also explain the reducing action of lignin and its methoxy value.

Chlorolignin has been found to give CO_2 on distillation with 12% HCl according to the method of Nanji, Paton and Ling (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1925, 44, 253T) even when hydrogen was passed instead of air. The percentage is higher than in HCl-lignin; it may be explained by the fact that the negative substitution by chlorine makes the adjacent COOH group more susceptible to hydrolysis. It is interesting to note in this connection that fructose but not glucose was found to give CO_2 in an atmosphere of hydrogen when similarly treated.

As shown in a previous paper, the mol. wt. of lignin must lie near about 830; the mechanism of chlorination can be satisfactorily explained on the basis that lignin has a mol. wt. of 816. Under ordinary conditions, 25.8% of Cl means 8 Cl atoms enter the molecule to give $C_xH_{y-8}O_zCl_8$. On being heated to 135-40° or treated with dilute NaOH in the cold, 3 atoms of Cl are lost as HCl to leave behind a compound with 5 Cl atoms in the molecule, *i. e.*, $C_xH_{y-11}Cl_5O_z$ (with 17.7% of Cl) and during chlorination of lignin at 60° or with catalysts the same product results. On re-chlorination, the original compound gives a product with 11 atoms of Cl, *viz.*, $C_xH_{y-11}Cl_{11}O_z$ (with 32.7% of Cl). The methoxy value also can be explained similarly. Two methoxy groups are present in chlorolignin, which means 5.67% of OCH_3 ; while 5.61% has actually been found. This view is supported by the fact that the mol. wt. of chlorolignin with 25.8% of Cl in phenol has been found to be 1080 by cryoscopic method; the theoretical value is 1090. By the boiling point method Waentig (*loc. cit.*) also got a similar figure for chlorolignin from straw. It is too premature to suggest any structural formula for lignin at this stage.

EXPERIMENTAL

Raw jute, freed from adhering impurities and fatty and resinous matter in the usual way, was dried over P_2O_5 under vacuum. Dry chlorine was passed into the gas-washer containing the jute for 10-12 hours. The fibre turned light yellow. Excess of chlorine was removed by passing dry air through the gas-washer and HCl by water. Chlorolignin was extracted with acetone. Cl in the sample was determined by Piria and Schiff's method, which was found to give the same result as Carius method (Found: Cl, 25.78 per cent).

The same sample of jute was moistened with water and chlorinated in the same way for 4 hours. The fibre turned golden yellow and towards the end it became much lighter. Purification was done in the same way (Found: Cl, 25.67 per cent).

Purified jute was boiled with 1% KOH for 1 hour and then chlorinated by moist chlorine in the same way. The reaction was complete in 1 hour, prolonged exposure did not increase the percentage of chlorine (Found: Cl, 25.64%; OMe, 5.64%).

2.7537 G. of purified jute was refluxed with 150 c.c. of KOH (equivalent to 282.0 c.c. of 0.882 N-HCl) for one hour and the

washings (until neutral) required 275 c.c. of the HCl, whence 1.25% KOH was absorbed by the jute.

Lignin was separated from jute with 42% HCl at 20° for 24 hours and without acid boiling at the end. Reducing sugars were removed by boiling the neutral lignin with water, the light grey product was free from pentosans. It was dried and finely powdered and then sieved through 200 mesh. About 2 g. of this were suspended in about 50 c.c. of CCl₄ in a gas-washer and Cl was passed for 4 hours while it was occasionally shaken. (Found: Cl, 25.88; OMe, 5.55 per cent).

Chlorination at 60° was done by placing the gas-washer with CCl₄ and lignin in a water-bath and passing Cl into the same. Purification was done as usual. Chlorolignin was heated in a glass tube at 140-50° in a glycerine bath until no HCl was found to evolve. The deep brown mass was washed with water until neutral and Cl was estimated in the sample. The results are shown below.

TABLE I.

Medium.	Time.	Temp.	Moist or dry.	Light or dark.	Cl.	Analysis OMe.
CCl ₄	4 hours	0°	Dry	Diffused	25.67%	5.31%
"	"	27	Moist	"	25.88	5.55
"	"	"	Dry	Sun light	25.81	5.64
"	"	"	"	Dark	25.72	...
"	"	28	Dry	Diffused	25.69	...
"	"	60	Moist	"	17.68	6.24
"	"	27	Dry	"	17.80	... with I ₂
"	"	"	"	"	17.77	... ,, SbCl ₃
"	"	"	"	"	17.81	6.41 ,, FeCl ₃
Acetic acid	"	29	Moist	"	25.90	6.83
"	1	"	"	"	17.27	...
CHCl ₃	4	"	Dry	"	25.48	5.40
CH ₃ OH	4	"	Moist	"	23.0	13.23
"	1	"	"	"	17.97	13.19
Water	4	"	"	"	25.31	1.52

CO₂ was estimated by boiling about 0.5 g. of chlorolignin with 100 c.c. of 12% HCl on glycerine-bath and slowly passing the gas with CO₂-free air through an upright condenser to two gas-washers each

containing 100 c.c. of $N/10$ -baryta for 4-5 hours. The supernatant liquid (25 c.c.) was titrated next day and CO_2 determined in the usual way.

Formaldehyde was estimated by distilling about 0.3 g. of the substance with 28% H_2SO_4 according to Tollens' method until the distillate gave no test by Schryver's reagent (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1910, 82B, 226). The filtered liquid was condensed with excess of dime-done dissolved in dilute NaOH and made just acid with acetic acid (Weinberger, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1931, 3, 365). This was kept at 4° for 24 hours after addition of a saturated solution of NaCl , filtered in a glass filter, washed with water until free from chloride, dried at 110° and weighed. The iodometric method gave too high results owing to the fact that it contained a product which gave iodoform under these conditions. The cyanide method could not be employed due to the fact that it contained traces of HCl .

The mol. wt. was determined by the freezing point method in phenolic solution. Care was taken to avoid moisture and not to allow the temperature of the surrounding bath to rise $2-3^\circ$ higher than that of the solution, as anomalous results were obtained otherwise. The results are shown in Tables II and III.

TABLE II.

Sample.	Cl.	OMe.	HCHO.	CO_2 .	Mol. wt.	Cl in product after NaOH treatment.	Cl in sample after heating to $135-40$.	Cl in re-chlorinated product.	OMe in re-chlorinated product.
Cl-lignin from jute	25.64%	5.61%	0.74%	4.20%	1080	17.70%	17.84%	32.74%	4.38%
„ from HCl -lignin	25.88	5.55	0.70	3.94	...	17.78	17.88	32.87	4.41
„ in H_2O	25.31	1.52	1074

TABLE III.

Chlorolignin from jute.		K for phenol = 72.		
Substance.	Phenol.	Δ in 0°	Mol. wt.	Mean.
(i) 0.2470 g.	19.11 g.	0.085	1095	
(ii) 0.1522	22.62	0.045	1067	1080
(iii) 0.2015	20.56	0.065	1078	

Chlorolignin from HCl-lignin in aqueous suspension.

Substance.	Phenol.	Δ in 0°	Mol. wt.	Mean.
(i) 0.2140 g.	20.42 g.	0.070	1077	
(ii) 0.1876	22.06	0.055	1113	1074
(iii) 0.2206	21.52	0.075	1032	

Ratio of Cl: HCl.—0.3 to 0.4 G. of dry powdered and sieved lignin and 50 c. c. of CCl_4 (dry) were taken in a gas-washer and dry chlorine gas was passed through it very slowly (1 to 2 bubbles per second). This gas-washer was connected to a second washer containing about 100 c. c. of water. The latter was wrapped with a thick black cloth to minimise the formation of HCl. After the reaction, excess of Cl was removed by passing dry air, during which process all the CCl_4 evaporated off. Absence of Cl was tested by starch-iodide paper. In some cases it was necessary to place the gas-washer containing water on boiling water while air was passed through it. The chlorolignin was carefully removed quantitatively, washed with water until neutral, dried and Cl was estimated as before. The washings were added to the gas-washer containing aqueous HCl and total HCl was estimated by titration with $N/10$ -alkali in the usual way. As a little HCl was still formed by the action of chlorine on water even when it was covered with black cloth, it was necessary to perform a blank experiment with the same quantity of water and for the same time, and the titre for HCl (about 4 c. c. of $N/10$ -NaOH) deducted from the volume of NaOH. The amount of HCl was always slightly higher than the Cl combined. This is explained by the fact that during removal of chlorolignin, slight traces imperceptively remained on the walls of the gas-washer.

TABLE IV.

Lignin.	Time.	Temp.	Cl as HCl.	Cl in combination.	Ratio $\frac{\text{Cl}}{\text{HCl}}$.
0.3029 g.	4 hrs.	28°	0.1506 g.	0.1404 g.	1.07
0.3080	3	28	0.1314	0.1264	1.04
0.2860	1	29	0.1126	0.1006	1.11
0.2575	„	60	0.0865	0.0780	1.10
0.2015	„	60	0.0758	0.0740	1.03

SUMMARY.

1. Dry Cl acts on dry jute to give a chlorolignin with the same percentage of Cl as moist Cl; but the reaction is very slow.

2. The effect of boiling KOH (1 % for 1 hour) on chlorination appears to be more physical than chemical.

3. Light has no influence on chlorination; in presence of catalysts like I_2 , $FeCl_3$ or $SbCl_3$ as also at 60° the maximum Cl-content was 17.7 % only.

4. Besides chlorination, methylation takes place when lignin is chlorinated in presence of methyl alcohol.

5. By careful chlorination, the same chloro compound (with 25.8 % of Cl) is always obtained provided the time is 4 hours and lignin is very finely powdered.

6. The percentage of Cl falls down to 17.7 if the chlorolignin is treated with dilute NaOH at room temperature as well as when it is heated to $135-40^\circ$ for 3-4 hours.

7. By estimating Cl as HCl and that in combination, it has been shown that HCl-lignin contains no double bond.

8. The chlorolignins from jute and separated lignin have been shown to be almost identical.

9. Chlorolignin gives CO_2 even in an atmosphere of hydrogen when boiled with 12% HCl, this is probably due to a COOH group in lignin.

10. The dioxymethylene is partially lost during chlorination as also the methoxy.

11. By acid or alkali distillation chlorolignin gives a product which gives iodoform with iodine and alkali.

12. The mechanism of chlorination can be explained by assuming that lignin has a mol. wt. of 816.

13. No structural formula for lignin so far proposed can adequately explain the above reactions.

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